
Science and Theology: Befriending Each Other Epistemically

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Abstract: The author wants to indicate the need for dialogue between science and religion for the sake of human wellbeing. Science and theology have ever been the two most powerful and influential enterprises of humans determining the properties of their very being and defining the destiny of the humanity at large. The dictums and contours of the world of their meaning have been extensively processed by science and theology. The apparent dissonance between them, as was vivid in the past and even today, leaves one amused as to their meaning-making task besides raising several serious fundamental questions. Given the interwoven and overarching framework of their enquiry, what justification is there for the discordant note that they strike with each other? The tension between the religious experience and the quest for an absolute and certain knowledge, does it betray a fundamental dichotomy in the very structure of our rationality or our failure to reconcile the seemingly opposing elements of our knowledge-process? The

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belief in the fundamental unity of human rationality and the concern of science and theology with fundamental questions refuse to admit a fundamental dichotomy at their conceptual domains. There can be no tension between truth and truth. Once we discover the unitary conceptual grounds and frameworks of interaction, we will be able to identify the real problem in the apparent discordance between science and theology. The author argues that the assimilation and integration between science and religion becomes an imperative for the humanity as well. He agrees with Whitehead that “When we consider what religion is for mankind, and what science is, it is no exaggeration to say that the future course of history depends upon the decision of this generation as to the relations between them”

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Science and theology have ever been the two most powerful and influential enterprises of humans determining the properties of their very being and defining the destiny of the humanity at large. ¹ The dictums and contours of the world of their meaning have been extensively processed by science and theology. The apparent dissonance between them, as was vivid in the past and even today, leaves one amused as to their meaning-making task besides raising several serious fundamental questions. Given the interwoven and overarching framework of their enquiry, what justification is there for the discordant note that they strike with each other? The tension between the religious experience and the quest for an absolute and certain knowledge, does it betray a fundamental dichotomy in the very structure of our rationality or our failure to reconcile the seemingly opposing elements of our knowledge-process? The belief in the fundamental unity of human rationality and the concern of science and theology with fundamental questions refuse to admit a fundamental dichotomy at their conceptual domains. There can be no tension between truth and truth. Once we discover the unitary conceptual grounds and frameworks of interaction, we will be able to identify the real problem in the apparent discordance

between science and theology. Once the problems are identified we learn to ask the right questions on issues of dissonance.

Revelation Revisited

Traditionally theology has been defined as “the faith seeking understanding.” The data of this enterprise come from revelation and tradition. The revelation that has taken place in history is encoded in the Scripture. Personal experience of God and its expressions in various forms constitute the norm of truth and authority to which believers respond in faith. The language of revelation, so fundamental to religious epistemology is a profound proclamation before the humanly constructed epistemological modalities testifying to the non-rational and supernatural horizons of truth, over and above the rational and natural domains. Revelation comprehended in its proper sense will be a holistic activity subsuming and subserving all other modes of knowing. For this, the hermeneutical matrix and the interpretative tools of revelation must be as holistic and as dynamic as the content of any authentic revelation. The process of understanding the “historical” revelation will be an ongoing hermeneutical enterprise so as to encounter the trans-historical aspects of the divine mysteries.

Nevertheless, the apologetic writings relying heavily on rational and historical evidences for the legitimization of revelation have tended to enclose it into quite parochial frameworks of reason, history, etc. The categories of revelation have been conceived of as products than processes. When the language of revelation is conceived as complete in itself, a beleaguered recourse to faith alone becomes the only way to comprehend them. This realist approach towards revelation with its consequent faith reductionism have forced the compartmentalization of itself as yet another mode of knowing, often in tension with other modes, perpetuating a radical dichotomy at the heart of the activity of knowledge. Truth has been considered as an object to be preserved in custody. The extreme reliance on faith and static outlook towards truth seem to have alienated the revelatory truth from cognitive and natural credibility.

The final outcome was a systematically produced disillusionment in at least some of the hearers of revelation.

The claims of the supremacy of authority was evident in the statement of Pope Pius XII: "Investigations in science may go forward as long as all are prepared to submit to the judgment of the Church...." (Pius XII, 1990: 181). The claims of the supremacy of revealed knowledge on supernatural grounds is very vulnerable to critical assault, because the parochial understanding of theology of the supernatural as well as natural rules out the critical analysis of the fundamental assumptions of its own categories. An adequate knowledge of the material, physical, and biological aspects of the object of description ever escaped the attention of dogmatic formulations. Hence at the basis of theological knowledge was a set of static categories.

This is not to overlook the hermeneutical or mystical consciousness of theology. Despite the awareness of the historical and cultural dependence of the theological statements, a serious consideration of the material and the organic matrix and the laws and principles governing it which permeate every animate and inanimate being still eludes theology. The Scripture had underscored the role of the created realities in unraveling the mystery of the creator. "They shall not hurt or destroy in my entire holy mountain; for the earth shall be full of the knowledge of the LORD as the waters cover the sea" (Is.11:9 RSV). "Ever since the creation of the world, the invisible existence of God and his everlasting power have been clearly seen by the minds understanding of created things" (Rm.1:20). In the fourth century St. Augustine had called nature the prime Word of God. However it is doubtful whether these verses have obtained sufficient attention in Christian thinking more than their rhetorical and aesthetic values, except for a few mystical traditions.

In the modern times, the serious challenge to the taken-for-granted assumptions of the theological fundamentals comes from physics and philosophy. Although history and historical categories are fundamental to Christian theology, except for the cultural

and social dimensions, the more fundamental nuances of being historical like space, time, etc., seem to have eluded Christian theology. The ever progressive understanding of the scientific fundamentals like space, time, matter, energy, etc., can revise the often static and deterministic nature of such concepts in theology. And as we discover the full nuances of the very fundamentals of theology many of the supernatural might turn out to be quite natural or some of the “natural laws” might be proved to be only “human laws.”

A thousand years ago, Western philosophy had raised the splendid question: what is a thing? The epistemological crisis that still haunts the Western philosophy has shown that asking “what is a thing” is also to ask “what does it mean ‘to be’?” (Isham, 1993: 81-82). As the foundations of science and philosophy are shaken by the epistemological “revolutions” of the times, a credible theological proposition that does not submit itself to such serious and fundamental epistemological scrutiny will not be able to withstand the test of the times. Unless the natural and inward dynamisms of revelation are explored with critical acumen, revealed set of truths, the very starting point of theology itself would be proved to be a secondary reality. Such an introspective operation would reassert revealed knowledge itself as not that non-cognitive or non-objective as we have made it of. This will be the great epistemological awakening into the unity of knowledge dispelling the stubbornly persistent illusion of the dichotomy between reason and faith.

There are schools of thought which still uphold the supremacy of religious premises on a discordant note. “Religious thought is concerned with language and with the riddle of life, and has no need to defer to highly specialized and marginalized forms of technical expertise (like science)” (Cuppitt, 1990: 4): “Yet it is not clear if viewing God ‘within’ nature (as implied by the scientific worldview) is any better than seeing him ‘outside’ of nature...” (Langsfeld, 1997: 111). These statements only betray the intellectual addiction to the traditional dualistic epistemology. It is

slightly surprising that St. Augustine had a challenging response to such thinking in the fourth century itself:

It often happens that even a non-Christian knows a thing or two about the earth, the sky, the various elements of the world, about the movement and revolution of the stars and even their size and distance.... How are they going to believe our books concerning... the kingdom of heaven when they think they are filled with fallacious writing about things which they know from experience or sure calculation? There is no telling how much harm these rash and presumptuous people bring upon their more prudent brethren when begin to be caught and argued down by those who are not bound by the authority of our Scriptures, and when they then try to defend their flippant, rash, and obviously erroneous statements by quoting a shower of words from those same Sacred Scriptures, even citing from memory those passages which they think will support their case (Cited in Macior, 1997: 30-31).

It is an optimistic fact that the Church has come to this realization, as evident in the words of Pope John Paul II: "It (Theology) must be in vital interchange today with science.... Theology will have to call on the findings of science to one degree or another as it pursues its primary concerns for the human person,.... Can we not hope that the sciences of today,... may invigorate and inform those parts of the theological enterprise that bear on the relation of nature, humanity and God?" (Cited in Russell, 1990: M11, M12).

Another imperative for the intersection of science and theology is generated by culture. The praxis of modern culture, including its life-styles, values, metaphors, language, myths, etc., have been generated and dominated by science. The scientific culture is universal because, as Peacocke has rightly judged, "today one of the universal languages of humanity cutting across all cultural boundaries is that of science" (Peacocke, 1989: 11). The meaningful articulation of the theological truth in a scientific age necessitates an integration of the reliable scientific insights into theology. "We need to apply our reason to our sources - the Bible, the tradition.... The contemporary person needs to hear the word that is eternally

uttered by the creator to his creation in a language that he or she can understand and respond to” (Peacocke, 1989: 11). Thus science can enable theology for a praxis based cross-cultural theology. The moral values and standards advocated by theology without scientific plausibility will be theologically arbitrary and socially unappealing.

Science as Hermeneutical

As regards science, the necessary corollary of the awareness of the unity of knowledge is openness for constructive dialogue with theology. The methodic and epistemic challenges in the self understanding of science, as discussed earlier, have dispelled the unjustified claims associated with physical and mathematical realism. Physicist Despagnat’s classic distinction between “the meaningful” and “the scientifically meaningful” as suggested by the terms themselves provide a solid analogy to the demarcation between the finite horizons of meaning possessed by science and the infinite horizons transcending it. Given that the megalomaniac claims of the scientific theories of the past are untenable and also given the new metamorphic and evolutionary understanding of them, science itself is to be viewed as a dynamic hermeneutic enterprise. More than a custodian of truth, it is a candidate for reality always open to modification and correction from the data, more accurate concepts and models.

An extrinsic dynamism that can enhance the scientific picture of reality is recognition of the relation of its truth with the religious truths. “A scientific community that ignores the relation of its truth and its life to law, to morals, and to fundamental religious symbols... only makes itself and its culture vulnerable to ideological capitulations. Ignorance of the religious in both its demonic and its creative forms can be even more fatal for a scientific culture than ignorance of new scientific and technological developments” (Gilkey, 1986: 68).

It is necessary that those scientifically trained thinkers venturing on the coupling of the scientific discoveries with theology have the

preliminary knowledge of theology as well. One author's serious contention is that the number of individuals in the universe must be finite if God is to be able to exercise care for each (Ellis, 1988: 384-386). Another author's crucial anxiety is "can God escape the consummation of the world?" (Worthing, 1996: 159). Physicist Davies Paul thinks that the speculated presence of humans on other planets causes serious problems to the Christian doctrine of incarnation whereby Christ was born only on this earth (Davies, 1987: 11). Such theological anxieties only betray the unequipped and unreflective juxtaposition of science and theology.

There is much more a broadening of the scientific horizons necessary for a full length appropriation of the theological beauty into the sciences, although it may be presumptuous to imagine so much and science may not be science as such as understood today at such a level of knowledge. The scientific assumptions on uncertainty, indeterminacy, etc., are not to be viewed as a retreat to the human pursuit after truth, but as an awakening into the innumerable polyvalence of truth and reality. This is a momentum towards the replacement of the reductionist strategies with the holistic approaches. It is in completing the picture of truth that faith and theology come to the aid of science. Unlike the age-old theological intrusions into science through the God of the gaps, today the new scientific scenario is much conducive to a constructive accommodation of the rich theological metaphors. The God of the physicists, as some physicists would say, is the cosmic order. Science also has the profound insight into the inherent harmony of the entire creation. But, will science ever be able to call this order as a principle of love? Or, to identify this harmony as a supreme ultimate, say, the Father of Jesus Christ? The rich elusiveness of theology has many things at stake whereby it can play a vital role in complimenting, bettering, and even perfecting the picture of truth portrayed by the natural sciences. Vitalising the scientific reductionist caricatures and sweeping away the vacuum of the nihilist know-how-s of science are possible only with the collective elusiveness of the religious and theological themata.

Paul Davies must be right in saying that science offers us “a surer path to God than religion,” a path that can lead to several hitherto unknown polyvalence of truth. This is not a path that neither begins fully in sciences nor that ends fully with sciences, but a path that passes through the sciences. It is a path extending down through the history of the intellectual curiosity of the humanity. The scientific colouring of this path is so tempting and fascinating that it rejuvenates and re-invigorates any passer-by on it.

The Common Quest

The unity of experience entails the fundamental unity of the expressions. The unity of experience invalidates an ontological dichotomy in reality. A true apprehension of the metaphysical unity of beings enables us to look beyond the conceptually constructed dichotomies of expressions to the unifying thread among them, while preserving the methodic and epistemic distinctiveness of the diverse modes of expressions. This hermeneutical dialectic has been reinforced by the philosophical openings provided by modern sciences. The more-than-scientific contents of the scientific questions today is an authentic assertion of the ontological unity of the scientific formulations and theological expressions. “Every great scientific synthesis stimulates efforts to view the whole of reality in its terms.... But the views of reality that originate in this way are not in themselves scientific...” (Greene, 1962: 132). This new epistemological awareness of the metaphysical One in the many can very much remedy the conceptual polarizations and discontinuities of the theological knowledge. In transcending such polarizations we learn that there is more to revelation than we have so far “seen” or “heard.” God’s intervention in history is not an occasional or irregular activity, but the God who governs history is in a way the history itself. The mountains and plains where He has appeared and spoken give us the very vision and voice of God Himself. Metaphorically speaking, creation cannot be “finished” in just six days or the number of the patriarchs cannot be restricted to three.

The scientific analysis of the world discloses to us the metaphysical fabric of the unified milieu of mystery, experience and expression with its “de-materialization” of matter and “mystification” of the world and thereby the re-enchantment of the whole of reality. This tempting metaphysical fabric of natural knowledge in a way conceives of the entire cosmos as a metaphor in congruity with the metaphorical insinuations of the revealed knowledge. It enables us to articulate meaningfully the summit points of Christian revelation like the Holy Trinity, the Incarnation, the humans as the image of God, eschatology, etc. Our faith affirmations, confessional formulae, ethical exhortations, etc., would acquire broader implications and deeper applications in this endeavor.

As the deceptively held epistemological dichotomy between science and theology gets dispelled, we realize the pseudo nature of their conflict. “Never mind whether religion and science were really in conflict; they were increasingly *thought* to be in conflict.” Once the pseudo nature of the problem is identified there emerge the domains of substantive and constructive interaction between science and theology. If God is the all-encompassing reality, the biological, chemical and physical languages also will be evocative of a deeper experience of God. The theological claim of the divine unity of creation necessarily entails a coherent and unified conception of reality. As this totalistic view of reality begins to be mutually implicated and structurally shared by science and theology, both would transcend their finite horizons into the overarching horizons of truth and reality. Tremendous will be the implications of this fusion for the perennial issues of the human pursuit after truth, viz. God, world, and human. That sets the agenda for the rest of our inquiry. The assimilation and integration of it becomes an imperative for the humanity as well. As Whitehead has remarked: “When we consider what religion is for mankind, and what science is, it is no exaggeration to say that the future course of history depends upon the decision of this generation as to the relations between them” (Whitehead. 1981: 111)

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